

LINKING COMMUNITY-BASED ADAPTATION IN MITIGATING DISASTER: THE CASE OF CHEVAK NATIVE VILLAGE

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ABSTRACT

This research study investigated the level of awareness and difficulties faced by youth, adults, and elders in climate change adaptation, specifically focusing on the contribution of Community-Based Adaptation (CBA) approaches in enhancing the resilience of Chevak Native Village. A descriptive-correlational design is employed to assess respondents' knowledge, attitudes, and practices related to climate change. The findings indicate a moderate level of awareness among the respondents, highlighting areas for improvement in understanding, attitudes, and sustainable practices. Difficulties encountered by different age groups in adapting to climate change were identified, emphasizing the need for education, resources, and adaptation strategies to address the impacts and preserve cultural heritage. Statistical analyses reveal significant differences in awareness levels among different groups, emphasizing the importance of further analysis to understand the specifics of these differences. Furthermore, a proposed community-based adaptation plan is presented, outlining measures such as teacher training, curriculum integration, community engagement, and tribal involvement to address climate change challenges in Chevak Native Village. Overall, this research study provides valuable insights for science education, community engagement, and effective adaptation strategies in the face of climate change and disaster mitigation.

Keywords: *Adaptation, Attitude, Knowledge, Mitigation, Practices*

INTRODUCTION

Climate change presents a formidable challenge to communities worldwide, particularly to indigenous populations like the Chevak Native Village in southwestern Alaska. These communities face unique vulnerabilities due to their reliance on subsistence practices deeply rooted in their cultural heritage. The Chevak Native Village, for instance, depends on fishing and hunting for sustenance, community cohesion, and the preservation of their cultural identity (Johnson, 2011). However, recent climatic events, such as the historic 2022 storm and Typhoon Merbok, have underscored the urgent need for effective climate adaptation strategies. These events caused widespread damage, disrupting food security, damaging subsistence tools, and threatening the integrity of intergenerational camps.

In response to these challenges, the community has sought to develop a Community-Based Adaptation Plan (CBAP), which leverages the collective wisdom of its people. The CBAP is centered on indigenous knowledge and seeks to incorporate community engagement and traditional practices into its framework (Ristroph, 2021). This approach aligns with global recognition of the importance of integrating indigenous ecological knowledge into climate adaptation strategies (Bayrak et al., 2020). Indigenous knowledge, often passed down through generations, offers a nuanced understanding of environmental changes, enabling communities like Chevak to build resilience against climate-related disasters (Ristroph, 2019; Buzard et al., 2023).

Alaskan native communities are particularly vulnerable to climate change impacts, especially in the face of rapid environmental shifts such as permafrost thaw, coastal erosion, and extreme weather events (Tran et al., 2020). The northern regions, including Alaska, are experiencing these changes more acutely, with significant implications for the traditional ways of life that are critical to indigenous identities (Ristroph, 2021). As such, the need for robust, locally tailored adaptation strategies has become increasingly apparent (Balehegn et al., 2019).

The role of education, particularly in the field of science education, is crucial in fostering awareness and preparing communities for the impacts of climate change. Education empowers communities by providing them with the knowledge and tools necessary for effective adaptation (Sriyanto et al., 2019). Furthermore, the integration of climate change education into formal and informal settings can enhance the adaptive capacity of future generations (Rajapaksha & Sandamini, 2021).

This research study seeks to explore the extent to which Community-Based Adaptation approaches can mitigate the impacts of climate change in Chevak Native Village, focusing on the role of indigenous knowledge, education, and community engagement in fostering resilience. By examining the level of awareness, challenges faced, and the effectiveness of the proposed CBAP, this study contributes valuable insights into the ongoing global discourse on indigenous-led climate adaptation efforts. By identifying the unique challenges each group faces, the research aims to propose a tailored community-based adaptation plan (CBAP) that incorporates both traditional

ecological knowledge and modern adaptation strategies. This approach will strengthen the community's resilience to climate impacts while preserving cultural heritage and promoting intergenerational knowledge sharing.

Research Questions

1. How may the profile of respondents be described in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age;
 - 1.2 Gender;
 - 1.3 Marital Status;
 - 1.4 Educational Attainment;
 - 1.5 Role in the Community;
 - 1.6 Occupation;
 - 1.7 Length of Stay in the Area; and
 - 1.8 Climate Change Disaster Experience?
2. How may the level of awareness among the respondents be described in terms of
 - 2.1. Knowledge;
 - 2.2. Attitudes; and
 - 2.3. Practices toward climate change adaptation?
3. How may the climate change difficulties that the respondents encounter be described?
4. Are there significant differences between and among the answers of the respondents?
5. Based on the findings of the study, what Community-based Adaptation Plan (CBAP) may be proposed to the Chevak native village council?
6. What are the implications of the study to science education?

METHODOLOGY

The research study, conducted from the year 2023 until the first quarter of 2024, followed a descriptive-correlational design aimed at investigating the level of awareness and the adaptation difficulties faced by the residents of Chevak Native Village. The research sought to explore how community-based adaptation (CBA) approaches can enhance the village's resilience to climate-related disasters. A descriptive approach was utilized to describe the current state of awareness among respondents regarding climate change adaptation, while the correlational aspect of the study examined the relationships between demographic variables and respondents' awareness levels.

The study utilized both face-to-face and online methods to gather data from the community members, including youth, adults, and elders. The participants were selected using snowball sampling, a non-probability sampling technique often employed when respondents are difficult to reach or when the target population is small. Snowball sampling allowed the researcher to identify a diverse set of respondents by using initial

participants to recommend others. This method was especially useful for ensuring that the study captured a wide range of perspectives across different age groups.

To collect the required data, a structured questionnaire was designed based on validated instruments from previous studies on climate change awareness. The questionnaire was divided into three main sections: personal demographics, level of awareness of climate change adaptation (knowledge, attitudes, and practices), and the difficulties encountered in adapting to climate change. A 4-point Likert scale was used to assess the respondents' awareness, with options ranging from "Highly Aware" to "Unaware." The instrument was subjected to a reliability test using Cronbach's alpha to ensure internal consistency, with results indicating a high level of reliability for the constructs being measured.

The data collection process involved distributing the questionnaires physically to respondents during face-to-face interactions and through Google Forms for online participation. The researcher collected data from a representative sample of the Chevak community, ensuring enough responses from each age group to facilitate meaningful analysis. The total sample size was calculated based on a 95% confidence level and a 5% margin of error, and the participants' responses were recorded and analyzed.

Descriptive statistics, including percentages and frequencies, were used to summarize the respondents' demographic profiles, while weighted mean scores were calculated to determine their level of awareness of climate change adaptation. Additionally, the research employed ANOVA (Analysis of Variance) and post-hoc tests to identify significant differences between the groups based on their demographic characteristics. These statistical methods allowed the researcher to explore whether variations in age, gender, or educational attainment had any significant effect on respondents' knowledge, attitudes, and practices concerning climate change adaptation.

Ethical considerations were strictly adhered to throughout the study. Participants were informed about the purpose of the research, and informed consent was obtained before any data collection took place. The researcher assured respondents that their personal data would be kept confidential and used solely for academic purposes. Additionally, the study followed privacy laws and guidelines, such as the U.S. Privacy Act of 1974, to protect the respondents' information.

In summary, this methodology employed a combination of quantitative data collection techniques, statistical analysis, and ethical research practices to provide a comprehensive understanding of climate change adaptation within the Chevak Native Village. It aimed to propose a community-based adaptation plan based on the findings, which would assist in mitigating disaster risks while incorporating local knowledge and practices.

RESULTS

Figure 1.
Age Profile of the Respondents

Figure 2.
Gender Profile of the Respondents

Figure 3.
Marital Status Profile of the Respondents

Figure 4.
Educational Attainment Profile of the Respondents

Figure 5.
Role in the Community Profile of the Respondents

Figure 6.
Occupation Profile of the Respondents

Figure 7.
Length of Stay Profile of the Respondents

Figure 8.
Climate Change Disaster Experience Profile of the Respondents

Table 1
Respondents' Level of Awareness: Knowledge in Climate Change Adaptation (CCA)

PARAMETER INDICATORS	ASSESSMENT MEAN			WEIGHTED MEAN	VERBAL INTER- PRETATION
	Youth	Adults	Elders		
1. Climate change is real, that is, it is taking place.	3.74	3.04	2.58	3.12	M
2. Scientific evidence on climate change is reliable.	3.60	3.27	2.00	2.95	M
3. The human community can control climate change.	3.44	3.28	2.50	3.07	M
4. Overall, climate change is bad; it is more harmful than beneficial.	3.48	3.27	3.00	3.25	H
5. Manifestations of climate change differ from one climatic region to another.	3.48	3.11	2.58	3.06	M
6. Climate change is inevitable because of the nature and style of modern life.	3.36	3.42	3.00	3.26	H
7. Climate change is not just a natural fluctuation in temperatures of the Earth.	3.59	3.29	3.00	3.29	H
8. It is not late for the human community to do anything to stop climate change or reduce it.	3.39	3.29	2.83	3.17	M
9. The average minimum and maximum temperatures have increased anywhere on the Earth since 1900.	3.47	3.31	3.25	3.35	H
10. Climate change is the tangible, long-term change in weather variables that is associated with the increases in the concentrations of the greenhouse gases in the atmosphere.	2.50	3.11	2.92	2.84	M
11. Climate change is a result of human activities.	2.74	3.39	3.67	3.27	H
12. Deforestation is one of the causes of climate change.	2.62	3.38	2.92	2.97	M

13. Climate change resulted not mainly from the ozone hole.	2.76	3.33	2.50	2.86	M
14. The transportation sector contributes substantially to climate change.	3.24	3.32	2.92	3.16	M
15. Burning of fossil fuel like oil and coal contributes to climate change.	3.50	3.34	3.25	3.37	H
16. The sector with the highest contribution to climate change is the energy sector.	3.50	3.18	3.42	3.36	H
17. Environmental pollution resulting from industry is one of the causes of climate change.	3.39	3.09	3.08	3.19	M
18. Effect of human activities on temperatures on the surface of the Earth is high.	2.44	3.08	2.17	2.56	M
19. Agricultural activities such as animal and plant production contribute to climate change.	2.67	3.38	3.00	3.02	M
20. The cause of climate change is the global warming associated with the increases in concentrations of greenhouse gases in the atmosphere.	2.55	3.12	2.42	2.70	M
21. Climate change causes biodiversity loss.	2.72	3.21	3.08	3.01	M
22. Climate change leads to soil fertility decrease.	3.38	3.49	2.83	3.23	M
23. Climate change contributes to increased wind and water erosion of soil.	3.39	3.30	3.17	3.28	H
24. Climate change brings about an increase in temperatures of the Earth all over the World.	3.57	3.22	2.92	3.24	M
25. The human community currently experiences the effects of climate change and suffers from them.	3.72	3.17	2.67	3.19	M

26. Climate change leads to a decrease in incidence of contagious and infectious plant, animal, and human diseases.	3.48	3.09	3.17	3.25	M
27. Rise in water level in seas and oceans and submergence of islands and adjacent lands are results of climate change.	3.49	3.10	3.08	3.23	M
28. Shortage of water that is suitable for domestic use and irrigation of plants and animals may result from climate change.	3.08	2.95	2.33	2.79	M
29. Decline in plant and animal food production, and, hence, deterioration of food security, may result from climate change.	3.05	3.09	1.83	2.66	M
30. Climate change may cause an increase in the frequency and intensity of extreme weather conditions such as heat waves, drought, hurricanes, and heavy rains in some areas in the world.	2.94	3.09	2.25	2.76	M
GRAND MEAN	3.21	3.22	2.81	3.08	M

Legend: 3.25-4.00 – High (H); 2.50-3.24 – Moderate (M); 1.75-2.49 – Low (L); 1.00-1.74 – None (N)

Table 2
Respondents' Level of Awareness: Attitude towards Climate Change Adaptation (CCA)

PARAMETER INDICATORS	ASSESSMENT MEAN			WEIGHTED MEAN	VERBAL INTER- PRETATION
	Youth	Adults	Elders		
1. Having a mindset that the climate is not changing.	3.46	2.89	2.50	2.95	M
2. Participating in planting trees that thrive on erosion.	2.47	3.04	2.08	2.53	M
3. Planting trees can help reduce the rate of climate change.	3.43	3.26	3.25	3.31	H

4. Refusing to listen to news about climate change adaptation.	3.48	3.29	2.92	3.23	M
5. Having prior knowledge of climate change adaptation.	3.46	3.10	3.17	3.24	M
6. Taking part in the dissemination of climate change news.	3.44	3.41	3.25	3.36	H
7. Reading any available information on climate change adaptation.	3.62	3.29	3.25	3.39	H
8. Climate change adaptation will benefit only those who caused it.	3.45	3.29	3.17	3.30	H
9. Studying all of the climate change information that is available.	3.47	3.31	3.42	3.40	H
10. Always asking questions on climate change adaptation strategies.	2.49	3.07	3.42	2.99	M
11. Getting ready to deal with the consequences of climate change.	2.71	3.40	3.67	3.26	H
12. Working hard to educate my friends about climate change adaptation.	2.63	3.39	3.58	3.20	M
13. Being seriously concerned with the problem climate change may bring.	2.73	3.34	3.42	3.16	M
14. Being pleased if schools begin to treat the topic of climate change more seriously.	3.25	3.31	3.58	3.38	H
15. Believing that the problem of Climate change adaptation will be easy to handle.	3.49	3.38	3.42	3.43	H
16. Participating in a climate change adaptation awareness club in the school to help.	3.49	3.22	3.25	3.32	H
17. Being worried at the rate of flooding because it increases the effect of climate change.	3.39	3.11	3.58	3.36	H

18. Spreading information about climate change adaptation within your area of location.	2.48	3.03	3.25	2.92	M
19. Predicating in planting of trees on open fields in order to check the incidence of erosion.	2.70	3.35	2.58	2.88	M
20. Having a mindset that decreasing the use of old vehicles can mitigate climate change impacts.	2.57	3.11	2.75	2.81	M
21. Urging friends to put an end to bush burning in order to mitigate climate change.	2.71	3.26	2.92	2.96	M
22. Trying to help the school or workplace to avoid climate change impacts.	3.39	3.48	3.33	3.40	H
23. Would not mind taking part in any activity to ensure proper climate change adaptation.	3.39	3.31	3.17	3.29	H
24. Not thinking that proper environment management could stop the impact of climate change.	3.57	3.26	2.67	3.17	M
25. Having the belief that harnessing climate change impact will bring about a safe environment.	3.73	3.15	3.33	3.40	H
26. Not feeling threatened about the problems caused by climate change e.g flooding, erosion.	3.48	3.10	3.17	3.25	H
27. Thinking that nothing can be done that that will create a significant impact on climate change adaptation.	3.47	3.13	3.17	3.25	H
28. Regarding adapting to climate change, there is little that people can do that will have a significant impact.	3.08	2.95	2.08	2.70	M
29. The belief that a lack of compliance to climate change adaptation strategies will	2.57	3.06	2.42	2.68	M

make a lot of people lose their job.					
30. Accepting the idea that the government should make an environmental law against anybody who will cause climate change.	2.71	2.85	2.08	2.55	M
GRAND MEAN	3.14	3.20	3.06	3.14	M

Legend: 3.25-4.00 – High (H); 2.50-3.24 – Moderate (M); 1.75-2.49 – Low (L); 1.00-1.74 – None (N)

Table 3
Respondents' Level of Awareness: Practices toward Climate Change Adaptation (CCA)

PARAMETER INDICATORS	ASSESSMENT MEAN			WEIGHTED MEAN	VERBAL INTER- PRETATION
	Youth	Adults	Elders		
1. Building of sea banks.	3.44	3.49	2.67	3.20	M
2. Control burning of bushes.	3.34	3.49	1.75	2.86	M
3. Increased use of wind energy.	3.33	3.48	2.92	3.24	M
4. Tree planting and reforestation.	3.27	3.26	3.17	3.23	M
5. Strengthening early warning sign.	3.52	3.36	2.92	3.26	H
6. Mapping of risk and disaster areas.	3.08	3.49	2.92	3.16	M
7. Helping people in evacuation areas.	3.08	3.52	2.83	3.14	M
8. Stop dumping of refuse in the drains.	3.09	3.43	3.08	3.20	M
9. Ensure that drains are cleared regularly.	3.26	3.33	3.00	3.20	M
10. Proper timing of tree planting activities.	3.03	3.16	2.67	2.95	M
11. Encouraging recycle of waste materials.	2.92	3.45	3.17	3.18	M
12. Creating awareness among the citizenry.	2.98	3.07	2.67	2.91	M

13. Awareness campaign on climate change.	3.12	3.22	2.83	3.06	M
14. Sticking to master plans of towns and cities.	3.12	3.59	3.08	3.26	H
15. Switching to early maturing varieties of crops.	3.17	3.47	2.83	3.16	M
16. Knowledge of routine measures of water levels.	3.24	3.45	2.75	3.15	M
17. Explore other livelihoods other than agriculture.	3.31	3.26	2.83	3.13	M
18. Proper disposal of waste in the environment.	3.05	3.03	2.25	2.78	M
19. Free medicine from the government to flood victims.	3.11	3.34	2.67	3.04	M
20. Planting early maturing varieties of crops and vegetables.	3.00	2.83	2.75	2.86	M
21. Use of direct seeding method, which requires less water.	3.17	3.18	2.92	3.09	M
22. Encouraging recovery of by- products and scraps for reuse.	3.45	3.50	3.00	3.32	H
23. Formation of climate change clubs in schools and localities.	3.36	3.45	3.08	3.30	H
24. Switch to other crops that can tolerate floods and heavy rainfall.	3.59	3.52	2.67	3.26	H
25. Provision of relief materials from good spirited individuals and government.	3.77	3.18	3.08	3.35	H
26. Rehabilitation of destroyed infrastructure by the government.	3.59	3.24	2.92	3.25	M
27. Construction of embankments to keep water back against pollution of the wetland.	3.45	3.06	3.00	3.17	M

28. Mounting awareness campaigns through the radio and television on climate change adaptation.	3.09	3.12	1.83	2.68	M
29. Making policy and programmes that provide opportunities for the displaced communities to earn livelihood.	3.09	3.10	2.08	2.76	M
30. Establishing weather monitoring equipment in school compounds to forecast events in the atmosphere.	3.19	2.84	2.17	2.73	M
GRAND MEAN	3.24	3.30	2.75	3.10	M

Legend: 3.25-4.00 – High (H); 2.50-3.24 – Moderate (M); 1.75-2.49 – Low (L); 1.00-1.74 – None (N)

Table 4
Climate Change Difficulties Encountered by the Respondents on CCA

CC Difficulties Encountered by the Respondents	FREQUENCY			Total	Rank
	Youth	Adults	Elders		
<i>Lack of support on research and monitoring related to climate change adaptation</i>	19	0	0	19	6
<i>Having difficulties in walking to tundra</i>	5	0	0	5	13
<i>Lack of knowledge in the proper disposal of waste</i>	4	0	0	4	14
<i>More bluff erosion and coastal in low-area damage from storm surge.</i>	16	0	0	16	7
<i>Difficulty going to school during winter storm</i>	6	0	0	6	12
<i>Less awareness on weather and climate and related environmental conditions</i>	28	0	0	28	2
<i>Lack of opportunities to learn about how tribal members</i>	23	0	0	23	4

<i>across Yukon-Kuskokwim Delta region are adapting food preservation techniques.</i>					
<i>Lack of available relief materials during disaster</i>	2	0	0	2	16
<i>Less protection on tribal cemeteries from erosion</i>	13	0	0	13	8
<i>Lack of promotion on the use of traditional food preservation techniques</i>	3	6	0	9	9
<i>Lack of building capacity for addressing concerns about increased shipping and oil spills</i>	0	23	0	23	4
<i>Not updated on subsistence regulation in the native village</i>	0	1	0	1	17
<i>Stream Flooding</i>	0	21	1	22	5
<i>Lack of knowledge in teaching climate change</i>	0	33	0	33	1
<i>Lack of fishing boats</i>	0	2	0	2	16
<i>Disconnected families to subsistence resources.</i>	0	8	0	8	10
<i>Change in seasonal patterns affecting subsistence activities</i>	0	7	0	7	11
<i>Increased frequency of storms</i>	0	26	0	26	3
<i>Lack of knowledge on how to do CC adaptation in our subsistence</i>	0	16	0	16	7
<i>Scarcity of food during winter season</i>	0	0	2	2	16
<i>Higher stream water temperatures</i>	0	0	3	3	15
<i>Less tribal participation in subsistence management plan</i>	0	0	4	4	14
<i>Less tribal participation in subsistence management plan</i>	0	0	4	4	14
Total	119	143	12	274	

Table 5
Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on Respondents' Level of Awareness

ANOVA

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
<i>Knowledge</i>	Between Groups	1.912	2	.956	17.076	.000
	Within Groups	15.170	271	.056		
	Total	17.082	273			
<i>Attitude</i>	Between Groups	.389	2	.195	3.318	.038
	Within Groups	15.900	271	.059		
	Total	16.289	273			
<i>Practices</i>	Between Groups	3.339	2	1.670	24.095	.000
	Within Groups	18.779	271	.069		
	Total	22.118	273			

Table 6
Proposed Community-Based Adaptation Plan (CBAP) for Disaster Mitigation in Chevak Native Village

Priority	Goal	Objective	Adaptive Measures	Key Success Indicators	Partners and Sources of Technical Assistance	Cost and Sources of Funding	Follow-up
1. <i>Lack of knowledge in teaching climate change</i>	To address the lack of knowledge in teaching climate change by enhancing educators' understanding and capacity to effectively teach about climate change topics in an accurate, engaging, and inclusive manner.	To develop and implement comprehensive professional development programs for educators that address the lack of knowledge in teaching climate change, equipping them with the necessary information, resources,	1. Providing comprehensive and ongoing professional development opportunities for educators to enhance their understanding of climate change science, impacts and solutions.	1. Increased participation rates in professional development opportunities related to climate change. 2. Improved knowledge and understanding of climate change science among educators. 3. Implementation of innovative teaching methods related to climate change in classrooms.	1. Educational Institutions 2. Nonprofit Organizations 3. National and Local Government Agencies 4. Scientific Research Institutions 5. International Organizations 6. Teacher Associations and Networks 7. Online Platforms and Resources	Costs: 1. Curriculum development: Creating or updating teaching materials, textbooks, and resources specific to climate change education. 2. Teacher training: Providing professional development programs,	1. Strengthen the knowledge in teaching climate change

Link: <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1LnD1RVbAPjd0gQAesPGht3prOAOz3wEF/view?usp=sharing>

DISCUSSION

Figure 1 showed the age profile of the respondents, displaying the percentage distribution across different age categories: Youth, Adults, and Elders. The bar graph presents the distribution of age groups in terms of percentage within three categories: Youth, Adults, and Elders. Among the youth, the majority (52.10%) are between 13 to 14 years, followed by 41.18% aged 15 to 16 years, and a smaller percentage (6.72%) aged 17 years. In the adult group, the largest segment (27.97%) falls in the 18 to 25 years age range, with other age groups showing a more gradual decline: 16.78% are aged 26 to 33, 13.29% are 34 to 41, 21.68% are 42 to 49, and 20.28% are 50 to 57 years. In the elders' category, a significant majority (66.67%) are aged 65 to 70 years, while the remaining elder age groups show smaller proportions: 8.33% are aged 71 to 75, 16.67% are 76 to 80, and 8.33% are aged 81 to 85. This distribution highlights a dominant youth population concentrated in early teenage years, with adults and elders showing more balanced distribution in middle and older ages, respectively. Research indicates that youth are critical agents in climate change adaptation, as they actively engage in climate mitigation practices and take responsibility for reducing anthropogenic impacts (Scott-Parker & Kumar, 2018; Nayan et al., 2020). Conversely, older adults contribute significantly to adaptation strategies, bringing valuable perspectives on community resilience and adaptation (Salma et al., 2022; Abdullah et al., 2022).

Figure 2 depicts the gender profile of the respondents across three categories: Youth, Adults, and Elders. Among the youth, the majority are male (53.78%), while females make up 46.22% of this group. In the adult category, the gender distribution shifts slightly, with females representing a higher percentage (53.85%) compared to males (46.15%). Among the elders, there is a significant male majority, with 66.67% of the respondents being male, while females comprise 33.33%. This data suggests that while the youth category is relatively balanced in terms of gender, males dominate the elder group significantly, and females have a slight majority in the adult group. These gender distributions highlight varying dynamics in gender representation across different age groups within the population. Gender plays a pivotal role in shaping climate adaptation capacities. Studies have shown that gender differences influence the ability of individuals to cope with and adapt to climate change impacts due to social roles and control over resources (Assan et al., 2018; Ampaire et al., 2019). Therefore, gender dynamics in adaptation strategies need to be considered to ensure inclusivity and effectiveness (Phan et al., 2019; Mersha & Laerhoven, 2018).

Figure 3 illustrates the marital status of the respondents, categorized into Youth, Adults, and Elders. Among the youth, 100% of respondents are single, with no individuals reported as married or legally separated. In the adult category, the majority (49.65%) are married, while 31.47% are single, and 18.88% are legally separated. Among the elders, the majority (83.33%) are married, with 16.67% reported as single, and none legally separated. This data highlights a shift in marital status as respondents age, with a high prevalence of marriage among the adults and elders, and no cases of legal separation among the youth or elders. The data suggests that marriage is more common among

older respondents, while the youth remain single, reflecting typical life-stage trends. Studies have shown that marital status influences climate change adaptation, with married individuals often having stronger social support systems, which enhance their ability to adapt to climate change (Asare-Nuamah & Amungwa, 2021; Lawson et al., 2019). Marital status also intersects with other demographic factors, such as age and education, in shaping adaptation strategies (Bello et al., 2023).

Figure 4 presents the educational attainment of the respondents across three categories: Youth, Adults, and Elders. Among the youth, the majority (83.19%) are high school undergraduates, while 16.81% have graduated from high school. In the adult category, the highest percentage (60.84%) are high school graduates, followed by 30.77% who are high school undergraduates, and smaller percentages who are college undergraduates (6.99%) and college graduates (1.40%). Among the elders, 66.67% are high school graduates, while 33.33% have obtained a college degree. This data suggests that a large portion of the youth are still in the process of completing high school, while many adults and elders have completed high school, with a smaller percentage of adults pursuing higher education. Elders show a higher rate of college graduation compared to adults, reflecting an educational shift as respondents age. The data highlights the importance of high school education across all groups, while a significant proportion of elders have achieved higher education. Studies show that individuals with higher educational attainment are more likely to adopt adaptation strategies, as education equips them with the knowledge and skills needed to understand climate risks and engage in adaptation practices (Randell & Gray, 2019; Asfaw et al., 2018; Megabia et al., 2022).

Figure 5 illustrates the role in the community profile of the respondents, divided into categories of Youth, Adults, and Elders. Among the youth, the overwhelming majority (97.48%) are students, with small percentages serving as teacher aides (2.52%). In the adult category, the largest group (46.15%) are subsistence users, followed by teacher aides (11.19%) and teachers (9.09%). Additionally, small percentages of adults hold roles such as town council members (1.40%), tribal council administrators (2.80%), and parents (26.57%). Among the elders, the roles are more evenly distributed, with 50% serving as school district administrators, 16.67% as town council members, and 8.33% as school administrators. This data highlights that the youth are primarily focused on education, while adults engage more in subsistence activities and teaching roles. Elders tend to hold leadership positions, particularly in school administration and town governance, reflecting their experience and standing in the community. The data illustrates a clear progression from education in youth to community participation and leadership in adulthood and elderhood. Community leadership and involvement in subsistence activities are crucial for fostering community resilience to climate change, particularly in indigenous communities like Chevak (Nguyen-Trung, 2023; Arifin et al., 2021).

Figure 6 presents the occupation profile of the respondents, categorized into Youth, Adults, and Elders. Among the youth, the vast majority (97.48%) are unemployed, as expected given their primary role as students. A small percentage (2.52%) are in white-collar professional jobs, while none are engaged in blue-collar work. In the adult category, the majority (67.13%) are employed in blue-collar (skilled worker) occupations, with a

smaller portion (9.09%) in white-collar professions, and 23.78% unemployed. Among the elders, the majority (75%) are employed in white-collar jobs, followed by 16.67% in blue-collar occupations, and a small percentage (8.33%) who are unemployed. This data reflects the typical life stage progression, where most youth are unemployed and focused on education, adults are more likely to engage in blue-collar occupations, and elders tend to hold white-collar professional roles. The higher unemployment rate among adults compared to elders may suggest a transition phase in the working lives of adults, while elders, with their years of experience, tend to occupy more senior or professional positions. Individuals in subsistence and blue-collar jobs are often more vulnerable to environmental changes, while those in white-collar professions may have more resources to implement adaptive measures (Pakdemirli, 2020; Ristroph, 2021).

Figure 7 illustrates the length of stay of the respondents in their area, categorized into Youth, Adults, and Elders. Among the youth, the majority (68.91%) have stayed in the area for 16 to 20 years, followed by 28.57% for 11 to 15 years, and a small percentage (2.52%) for 6 to 10 years. In the adult category, there is a more varied distribution: 28.67% have stayed for 21 to 25 years, 27.27% for 26 to 30 years, 21.68% for 16 to 20 years, 5.59% for 31 to 35 years, and smaller percentages for other ranges. Among the elders, the vast majority (83.33%) have lived in the area for 71 years and above, with smaller percentages (16.67%) having stayed for 66 to 70 years. This data indicates that the majority of youth have spent most or all of their lives in the area, reflecting their early stages in life. Adults show more variation, with many having lived in the area for two to three decades. The elder category is notably characterized by long-term residents, with most having lived in the area for over 70 years, showcasing their deep-rooted connection to the community. Long-term residents, particularly elders, provide valuable insights into environmental changes and contribute to adaptation strategies through their knowledge of historical climate patterns and community needs (Hemmerling et al., 2019).

Figure 8 presents the climate change disaster experience profile of the respondents across three groups: Youth, Adults, and Elders. Among the youth, the most experienced disaster is severe storms, reported by 42.86% of respondents, followed by erosion (32.77%), ground failure (15.13%), and flooding (9.24%). In the adult category, severe storms (28.67%) and flooding (21.97%) are the most frequently experienced disasters, while ground failure (16.78%) and erosion (22.38%) are also noted by some respondents. Among the elders, the most frequently experienced disaster is flooding, reported by 58.33% of respondents, with smaller percentages having experienced ground failure (8.33%) and severe storms and erosion (both 16.67%). This data highlights that severe storms and flooding are the most common climate change-related disasters across all age groups, particularly among elders, where flooding is significantly more prevalent. The data suggests that elders may be more vulnerable to the impacts of flooding, while youth and adults are exposed to a wider range of disasters, including severe storms and erosion. Direct experiences with climate-related disasters shape communities' awareness and motivate collective action to mitigate future risks (Rai & Khawas, 2019; Abdulrashid, 2021).

Furthermore, Table 1 presents the respondents' level of awareness regarding knowledge in climate change adaptation (CCA) across three groups: Youth, Adults, and Elders. The assessment is based on various parameter indicators and is measured using weighted means, which are interpreted as High (H), Moderate (M), Low (L), or None (N). The grand mean score for each group reflects a moderate level of awareness, with Youth scoring 3.21, Adults 3.22, and Elders 2.81, resulting in an overall weighted mean of 3.08, interpreted as Moderate. Several indicators achieved a high level of awareness across different groups. For example, "Burning of fossil fuel like oil and coal contributes to climate change" received high scores (3.50, 3.34, 3.25) across all groups, with an overall weighted mean of 3.37. Similarly, indicators such as "Climate change is not just a natural fluctuation in temperatures of the Earth" (3.29), "The average minimum and maximum temperatures have increased anywhere on the Earth since 1900" (3.35), and "The energy sector has the highest contribution to climate change" (3.36) also received high awareness levels. Conversely, several indicators reflected a moderate level of awareness, such as the recognition that climate change causes biodiversity loss (3.01), the role of deforestation in climate change (2.97), and the impact of human activities on surface temperatures (2.56). The elders scored consistently lower on many indicators compared to youth and adults, particularly in areas such as the scientific reliability of climate change evidence and the ability of the human community to control climate change.

Additionally, Table 2 presents the respondents' level of awareness in terms of their attitudes towards Climate Change Adaptation (CCA), evaluated across three groups: Youth, Adults, and Elders. The assessment includes various parameter indicators, each with mean scores for the groups, a weighted mean, and a verbal interpretation based on a defined scale where scores from 3.25 to 4.00 are considered High (H), 2.50 to 3.24 as Moderate (M), 1.75 to 2.49 as Low (L), and 1.00 to 1.74 as None (N). The grand mean scores reveal a moderate level of awareness among all groups, with Youth scoring 3.14, Adults 3.20, and Elders 3.06, resulting in an overall weighted mean of 3.14. This indicates that respondents generally exhibit moderate attitudes towards climate change adaptation. Attitudes play a crucial role in driving engagement in climate change mitigation efforts, with studies highlighting the importance of fostering positive attitudes toward adaptation practices (Asrat & Simane, 2018; Huyer & Partey, 2019). Several indicators received high levels of awareness. For instance, "Planting trees can help reduce the rate of climate change" received high mean scores across all groups (Youth 3.43, Adults 3.26, Elders 3.25), with a weighted mean of 3.31, interpreted as High. Similarly, statements like "Taking part in the dissemination of climate change news" (weighted mean 3.36), "Reading any available information on climate change adaptation" (3.39), and "Studying all of the climate change information that is available" (3.40) also reflected high awareness levels, suggesting that respondents are inclined to educate themselves and others about climate change adaptation. Additionally, proactive attitudes are evident in indicators such as "Trying to help the school or workplace to avoid climate change impacts" (weighted mean 3.40) and "Believing that the problem of climate change adaptation will be easy to handle" (3.43), both interpreted as High. These responses demonstrate a positive outlook and a willingness to engage in efforts to mitigate climate change effects. Conversely, some indicators reflected moderate levels of awareness. For

example, "Participating in planting trees that thrive on erosion" had a weighted mean of 2.53, indicating that active participation in specific environmental activities may be less prevalent. Similarly, "Accepting the idea that the government should make an environmental law against anybody who will cause climate change" received a weighted mean of 2.55, suggesting moderate support for stringent environmental legislation.

Table 3 presents the respondents' level of awareness concerning practices toward climate change adaptation (CCA), categorized into Youth, Adults, and Elders. The overall assessment, reflected in a grand mean of 3.10, indicates a moderate (M) level of awareness across all groups. Youth scored 3.24, adults 3.30, and elders 2.75, suggesting that elders have a slightly lower awareness of climate change adaptation practices compared to youth and adults. Several indicators received high (H) awareness levels, particularly in relation to community-driven or educational initiatives. For example, "Encouraging recovery of by-products and scraps for reuse" (3.32), "Formation of climate change clubs in schools and localities" (3.30), and "Switching to crops that can tolerate floods and heavy rainfall" (3.26) were practices with strong engagement across all groups. These responses indicate that respondents are aware of practical adaptation strategies, especially those that involve collective action and resource management. Other practices, such as "Strengthening early warning signs" (3.26), "Provision of relief materials" (3.35), and "Sticking to master plans of towns and cities" (3.26), also achieved high levels of awareness. These indicate a strong recognition of infrastructural and organizational responses to climate adaptation. However, there are several areas where respondents exhibited moderate awareness. For example, "Proper disposal of waste in the environment" (2.78) and "Establishing weather monitoring equipment in school compounds" (2.73) had lower awareness levels, particularly among elders. Similarly, "Mounting awareness campaigns through radio and television" (2.68) and "Making policies that provide livelihood opportunities for displaced communities" (2.76) also scored moderately, indicating that while respondents recognize these practices, they may not be actively engaged in them. Community-driven initiatives, such as climate clubs and collective action, are vital for successful adaptation (Nguyen-Trung, 2023).

Table 4 outlines the climate change difficulties encountered by respondents regarding climate change adaptation (CCA), ranked by frequency across Youth, Adults, and Elders. The most significant issue, with a frequency of 33 (reported by adults), is the "Lack of knowledge in teaching climate change," highlighting the need for improved educational resources. The second-ranked difficulty is "Less awareness on weather and climate and related environmental conditions" (28 responses), mainly reported by youth, underscoring the need for better environmental education. Adults also noted the "Increased frequency of storms" (26 responses), reflecting the impact of severe weather on their daily lives. Additionally, issues like "Lack of opportunities to learn about tribal food preservation techniques" and "Lack of capacity to address increased shipping and oil spills" (23 responses each) point to gaps in adaptation strategies. Some challenges, such as "Lack of support for research and monitoring" (19 responses) and "Stream flooding" (22 responses), were uniquely noted by youth and adults, respectively, while elders reported fewer difficulties, with "Scarcity of food during winter" being the most significant concern (2 responses). Overall, the data reveals that knowledge gaps, environmental

awareness, and adaptation capacity are the most pressing issues, particularly among youth and adults, highlighting the need for targeted education and support programs.

Table 5 reveals significant differences among Youth, Adults, and Elders in their knowledge, attitudes, and practices toward climate change adaptation (CCA), as indicated by the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). For knowledge, the F-value is 17.076 with a p-value of 0.000, indicating a highly significant difference between groups. Similarly, for practices, the F-value is 24.095 with a p-value of 0.000, showing substantial variations in how each group engages in CCA practices. The difference in attitudes, though significant, is less pronounced, with an F-value of 3.318 and a p-value of 0.038.

These statistical results indicate that youth, adults, and elders differ significantly in their levels of knowledge and practice, with some groups having better understanding and engagement in climate change adaptation efforts than others. The findings suggest that educational interventions and support systems are needed, particularly to enhance the knowledge and practices of groups lagging behind. Additionally, the moderate but significant differences in attitudes suggest that awareness campaigns and initiatives to foster positive perceptions of CCA could be beneficial. These efforts could lead to more consistent engagement across all age groups, ultimately contributing to more effective climate adaptation strategies at the community level.

Table 6 outlines a key component of the Community-Based Adaptation Plan (CBAP) for disaster mitigation in Chevak Native Village, focusing on addressing the lack of knowledge in teaching climate change. The plan emphasizes the need for comprehensive professional development programs for educators, equipping them with the knowledge, resources, and innovative teaching methods to effectively teach climate change adaptation. Success indicators include increased participation in professional development, improved understanding of climate science, and the integration of climate-related topics in classrooms. Partnerships with educational institutions, nonprofit organizations, and research bodies are highlighted as essential for technical assistance, while funding is allocated for curriculum development and teacher training. This part of the CBAP is crucial as it not only builds the capacity of educators but also ensures that climate change education reaches students and the broader community, thereby strengthening the village's overall resilience and preparedness for climate-related disasters.

The study's implications for science education are significant, particularly in the context of climate change adaptation. It highlights the need for science education to go beyond theoretical knowledge and focus on practical, community-based approaches that empower both educators and students to engage with real-world environmental challenges. By integrating climate change adaptation into the curriculum, educators can foster a deeper understanding of the science behind climate change and its impacts, while also equipping students with the skills and knowledge needed to develop solutions and become active participants in disaster mitigation efforts. This approach not only strengthens the scientific literacy of students but also promotes a more resilient and informed community, particularly in vulnerable regions like Chevak Native Village, where

the effects of climate change are directly felt. This study underscores the importance of professional development for educators, innovative teaching strategies, and collaborative efforts between educational institutions and local communities to effectively address climate challenges through science education.

Conclusions

The study concluded that respondents from different age groups varied in socio-demographic factors such as age, gender, marital status, education, community roles, occupation, length of stay, and climate disaster experiences. Despite moderate awareness of climate change, respondents showed a positive perception of scientific evidence and the benefits of tree planting. However, the study emphasized the need for greater focus on adaptation strategies and individual impact awareness to address climate challenges effectively. Additionally, age-related differences in climate change adaptation were identified, underscoring the need for tailored education and strategies to protect cultural heritage and better manage climate impacts. Significant differences in knowledge, attitudes, and practices were found among youth, adults, and elders, highlighting the necessity for evidence-based decision-making and more detailed analysis. A Community-Based Adaptation Plan (CBAP) was proposed for Chevak Native Village, aiming to tackle climate change through education, partnerships, traditional practices, and infrastructure improvements to enhance resilience and livelihoods. The study also stressed the importance of leveraging science education to address climate change and disaster mitigation by fostering community involvement, applying multidisciplinary approaches, and developing problem-solving skills to enhance understanding and engagement.

Recommendations

It is recommended that future research investigate the impacts of climate change disasters on different age groups to develop targeted and age-appropriate interventions. Additionally, awareness campaigns should be designed and implemented to promote proactive attitudes toward climate change adaptation across all demographic groups. Future studies should also focus on developing age-specific education and adaptation strategies to enhance the effectiveness of climate change responses. To better understand the variations in awareness levels among different age groups, further exploration is necessary. A longitudinal study is recommended to evaluate the long-term effectiveness of the proposed Community-Based Adaptation Plan (CBAP) in reducing vulnerability and increasing resilience within the community. Finally, further research should be conducted on the implementation and effectiveness of science education programs in fostering climate change involvement and enhancing problem-solving skills among learners.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study on linking community-based adaptation to disaster mitigation in Chevak Native Village was conducted with full adherence to ethical standards, ensuring all

research processes were in line with established ethical guidelines. Before data collection, informed consent was obtained from all participants, who were made fully aware of the study's purpose, procedures, and their rights, including the right to withdraw at any point without any repercussions. Participant privacy and confidentiality were strictly upheld, with all data anonymized to protect their identities, particularly given the sensitive nature of discussing climate change impacts and community adaptation. The study followed institutional ethical protocols and received approval from the relevant ethics review board, ensuring transparency and accountability throughout the research. In the context of climate change adaptation, the study maintained a focus on the active involvement of the community. The research sought to capture the lived experiences and insights of the Chevak Native Village residents, ensuring that all adaptation strategies proposed were rooted in the community's specific needs and environmental challenges. No conflicts of interest or biases influenced the study, and every effort was made to ensure the research's accuracy, honesty, and integrity. By integrating community-based perspectives and emphasizing the ethical treatment of participants, the study provides a reliable and socially responsible foundation for enhancing disaster mitigation strategies in the village.

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